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The Effect of Off-Farm Income Diversification on Households Economic Wellbeing amongst Rural Farm Households in East Gojjam Zone: An Endogenous Switching Approach

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ABSTRACT

The research was conducted with the objective of examining and studying the effect of off-farm activities on the economic wellbeing of selected rural households' in East Gojjam Zone. To do so, a primary data was collected from 620 selected households using structured, unstructured and focus group discussions. We employed a logit model to examine the determinants of participation off-farm activities and hence, the result of the model illuminates off-farm income diversification decision significantly depends on household head's education, age, family size, health status and community level infrastructures. The model also indicates that households residing closer to markets are more likely to diversify into off-farm activities than those in remote areas. To examine the effect of off-farm income diversification on the economic wellbeing of rural farm households' we employed endogenous switching model hence, this model accounts for selection bias resulting from unobserved factors that potentially affect farm households' decision to participate in off-farm activities. Consequently, the result of the model reveals that off-farm income diversification has a significant and positive impact on households' consumption expenditure and their food availability. Hence, this study concludes that off-farm income diversification is a true pathway for improving the economic wellbeing of rural farm households in rural areas of East Gojjam Zone.

Keywords: Off-farm activities; farm households; households' consumption expenditure; food shortage status; East Gojjam Zone.

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Chapter one

1. Introduction

This chapter deals with introduction part of the research that involves background of the study, statement of the problem, research question, objectives of the study (general and specific objectives), significance of the study, and clear delineation of the paper and its organization.

1.1. Background of the study

Now a day the changing in the socioeconomic, political, environmental and climatic atmosphere in developing countries across the globe has continued to aggravate the living conditions of most households especially those who are living in rural areas. Explicitly speaking, this problem is more severe in East African countries, where agriculture remains the main way of life and major source of employment (Woldehanna, 2000); but characterized by low level of productivity, slow growth, under-performance and high level of land fragmentations. Consequently, in rural economies, agriculture sector as an economic activity has not been consider as a sufficient vehicle for solving household-level malnutrition and food insecurity problems.

More pronouncedly, this incapability of agricultural sector to feed its ever increasing population in developing countries; has been increasing the vulnerability of those people who are often poor and deprived with a minimum standard of living (Bezabih et al., 2010). At an upshot, people in rural areas of low and lower middle income countries concentrate on minimizing risks and seeking food security by producing food for self-consumption. Hence, the impetus for achieving sustained rural economic development in rural areas has to pivot around expanding the base of off-farm activities (Escobal, 2001). Subsequently, rural off-farm sector has gained considerable importance as an alternative strategy for generating employment, reducing poverty, increasing the coping mechanisms in case of crop failures, and improving food security in rural economies.

Equivalent to other third world nations, factors like a frequent occurrence of floods that annihilating crops, large number of fragmented landholdings, unequal land distribution structure, and low use of modern agricultural inputs are threatening the livelihood sustainability of the rural people in Ethiopia, especially rural households in East Gojjam Zone (Nigisti, 2007). Explicitly

speaking, agriculture (i.e. backbone for Ethiopian economy) is one of the riskiest sectors of economic activity, prone to major shocks to both output and prices. Very often some rural households in Ethiopia, especially in East Gojjam Zone may not have enough food to consume in the lean season. Henceforth, it is clear that rural households in Ethiopia, especially in East Gojjam Zone urgently need ways of creating employment to absorb both the existing surplus labor and new entrants to the labor market. Hence failure to do so will not only limit economic growth but will also make it difficult to further reduce poverty levels and economic inequalities in the rural area (Holden, 2003). Accordingly, here off-farm enterprise can do a better job by hedge against both income and non-income poverty in rural areas in East Gojjam Zone.

To this extent, income earned from off-farm activities, in one hand; is used to finance agricultural expansion through the purchase of farming tools such as hoes and ox-ploughs, inputs like fertilizers and pesticides, and hiring agricultural labor (Mduma & Wobst, 2005); in other hand, income from off-farm activities used to pay school fees, health services, and food purchases (Bezabih et al., 2010). In a nutshell, having a diversified portfolio of income generating activities in Ethiopia, particularly in East Gojjam Zone is, therefore; a sure way to minimize income variability, to prevent rapid urbanization by providing youth employment and to ensure a minimum level of income for rural youths.

1.2. Statement of the problem

At a snapshot to the Ethiopian economy, the trend in the performance of agriculture sector indicates that the sector is under-performing and recorded slow growth rate over the past couple of years (Woldehanna and Oskam, 2001). Indisputably, in one hand, the share of gross domestic product (GDP) originating from agriculture has gone down and down from year to year in Ethiopian economy (Bezabih et al., 2010), on the contrary; the share of workforce engaged in agriculture, which was about 90 percent in 1990s, still remains at over 70 percent (Raphael and Matin, 2010). Consequently, this has led to widening of gap between incomes in agriculture and non-agriculture sectors, which is perceived to be one of the major reasons for persistence of poverty in the country. As a result, most rural households in rural economy engage in off-farm activities to hedge against both income and non-income poverty.

Henceforth, in developing countries, off-farm activities play a decisive role in sustainable development and poverty reduction trucks in rural economies. Unequivocally, off-farm activities can influence the rural economy through various channels. First, off-farm employment reduces the pressure on the demand for land in poor areas (Yesuf &Pender, 2005). Consequently, off-farm activities can contribute to breaking the vicious cycle of poverty in rural areas. Second, the income obtained from off-farm activities can significantly increase total household income and hence enhance the investment capacity in farm activities (Woldehanna and Oskam, 2001). Third, off-farm income is often a source of savings (Woldehanna, 2000), which plays an important role in food security. Overall, households that diversify their income in off-farm activities are more capable of overcoming negative shocks.

Despite the importance of off-farm economic activities to rural households in both social and economic terms; the sector lacks policy, financial and promotional support from the government, decision makers and development practitioners who are interested in rural development (Schwarze, 2004). As a result, rural off-farm economic activities are not achieving their full potential to provide benefits to participating households. Moreover, with the change in socioeconomic and climatic atmosphere in the country; the livelihood security of smallholder farmers in East Gojjam Zone is in a vulnerable condition (Bezabih et al.,2010), hence the goal of reducing poverty and improving a household's livelihood in the area has remained a challenging task. Consequently, a clear understanding of livelihood strategy, its outcome, and their impact factors is indispensable to unraveling the bottleneck of poverty and to formulate an effective anti-poverty program in the area.

Meanwhile, a lot of empirical studies have been documented on off-farm income diversification across the country, but there seems to existed dearth of empirical studies on the linkage effects of rural off-farm income diversification on economic wellbeing's among farm households in East Gojjam Zone. To contribute to the literature, this study is, therefore; examine the factors that determining the participation of rural off-farm activities, and the ways through which rural off-farm activities contribute to the economic well-beings of households in East Gojjam Zone.

1.3. Objectives of the study

1.3.1. General objective of the study

The general objective of the study is to examine the effect of rural off-farm activities on household's economic wellbeing amongst rural farm households in East Gojjam Zone, specifically in Shebel Berenta and Dejen districts.

1.3.2. Specific objectives of the study

Given the above general objective this study has the following specific objectives. This are:

- ✓ To examine the factors that determining the participation rural households' to rural off-farm activities in East Gojjam Zone.
- ✓ To examine the impact of rural off-farm activities on the households' economic wellbeing's in East Gojjam Zone.

1.4. Significance of the Study

The study focused on the role of off-farm activities in sustaining rural livelihood. The rural off-farm sector in Ethiopia is not an adequately researched component of the rural economy, and knowledge about its role in the broader development process is relatively little. Only few researches have been dealt with rural off-farm diversification activities in sustaining rural economic wellbeing. Hence, this study contributes to the understanding of the role of off-farm activities and the dynamics of rural off-farm economy in providing employment and income diversification opportunities. Results of this study will be important in providing information for governmental and non-governmental bodies who are working on off-farm activities for sustainable rural off-farm livelihood diversification. Moreover, it hopes to contribute to understand better the forces that drive change in rural off-farm economy, opportunities and constraints. Better understanding of the above will in turn be expected to contribute to the design and implementation of policies and instruments for the development of rural off-farm livelihoods of the rural poor.

1.5. Limitation of the study

The study focuses on the role of non-farm activities in sustaining rural livelihood that covers only 2 of the 21 districts which is purposely selected and limited, i.e. Namely, Shebel Berenta, and Dejen

districts. Therefore, the findings from the investigation are limited to the study area and the conclusions delineated may not be possibly represented as whole. So, future researchers may include other districts to generalize the findings and also to compare the results across the districts when it is practical. So, to generalize on findings, future searcher may include this in line with the others when it is practical.

1.6. Organization of the Paper

The paper is organized into five chapters. Chapter one have described the background of the study, statement of the problem, objective of the study, research question, significance of the study and scope & limitation of the study. After introducing chapter one chapter two reviews literature review with regard to the case study. The third chapter presents the methodology used. Chapter four discusses data presentation and analysis. Finally, the last chapter of the paper concludes the study and incorporates recommendations.

Chapter Two

2. Literature Review

2.1. Theoretical literature reviews

2.1.1. Introduction

This chapter discusses the literature on the factors that determine participation in livelihood diversification activities and its effect on the economic wellbeing of rural farm households' in East Gojjam Zone, Amhara regional state, Ethiopia, looking at both developed and developing countries perspectives. It also shows the existing literature on the independent variables that lead rural farmers to participate in livelihood diversification.

2.1.2. Definition of Terms and Concepts

Off-farm employment: defined as activities from which the farmers earn income apart from their farm work. It may include agricultural wage work on other people's farm, non-agricultural wage employment or self-employment in commerce, mining, manufacturing, transport, and services sector. Thus, unlike off-farm employment off-farm employment, is broader concept used to denote all works (agricultural or non agricultural) performed outside the own farm.

Off-farm employment: includes all activities other than agricultural work at the own farm and labor on another farm from which the farmers earn income.

Off-farm income: is the income earned from all sources excluded the income from the household's own farm or rented in plot.

Farm income: is the income from the farm households own farm or rented in plot, which includes net income from crops and animals.

Crop income: is obtained by subtracting gross costs from the volume harvested times median sales prices at the regional level.

Livestock income: consists of net income from sold live animals and both consumed and sold raw animal products, such as meat, eggs, milk, skin etc. Net livestock income is obtained by subtracting gross production expenditure from the quantity of animals sold times producer median prices and the quantity of produced raw animal products time's consumer median prices in the relevant region.

Household income: consists of all receipts in cash, in kind or in services that are received by the household or by individual members of the household at annual or more frequent intervals, but excludes windfall gains and other such irregular and typically one-time receipts (ILO, 2003). It is the sum of off-farm employment income, farm income, and non-labor income from rented out assets, remittance, inheritance, social benefits, and net transfers.

Participation: the act of taking part or sharing in some activities.

Household: is defined in this research as people living under the same roof and eating food from the same pot. That is, a household member who did not live independently during the survey time at least for six months.

Rural: is any locality that exists primarily to serve agricultural hinterland.

Rural household: is a household that lives in the countryside and that may involve in both farm and off-farm activities

2.1.3. Livelihood Diversification: Conceptual Foundation

Different terms such as off-farm, on-farm and off-farm are used to show diversification of activities and incomes. According to Barrett and Reardon (2000), the rural households activities and the corresponding income can be grouped using a three-way classification by sector (e.g., farm versus off-farm), function (wage versus self-employment), and space (local versus migratory). The classification of activities based on sector follows the distinctions of national accounting systems as primary (agriculture, mining, and other extractive activities), secondary (manufacturing), and tertiary (services). This leads directly to the distinction between agricultural or farm income and non-agricultural or off-farm income. Hence, It does not matter where the activity takes place (on the farm premises, in town or abroad), at what scale (in a huge factory or by a single person), with what technology, or whether the participant earns profit or labor income (wages or salary) from the activity (Barrett et al., 2001).

The second is functional classification. This includes wage employment (i.e., involving in wage or salary contract) and self employment (e.g., entrepreneurial activity). Given the sectoral and functional classification of an activity, the third one is spatial classification (local and migratory) which in turn holds some important sub categories (Barrett & Reardon, 2000; Barrett et al., 2001). Local activities are divided in to two sub categories (i) “at home or on-farm” (ii) “local away from home or off-farm”. On the other hand, migratory or “distant away from home” activities can be

categorized further in to: (a) domestic rural (e.g., inter-zone migration), (b) domestic urban (such as to a distant metropolitan area), and (c) foreign. From the three-ways of classification presented above, this study emphasis on spatial classification (on-farm/off-farm type). People in most part of the world (rural or urban) diversify their income. They collect their income from different sources, hold their wealth in different assets or use their assets in more than one activity. Before, we try to state the rationale for households livelihood diversification it is better to define what income diversification refers to.

The definition for income diversification differs among authors. Ersado (2003) defined income diversification as an increase in the number of sources of income or the balance among the different sources. Delgado and Siamwalla (1997) defined diversification as the switch from subsistence food production to the commercial agriculture. Others authors for example, Escobal (2001) define income diversification as an expansion in the importance of off-farm income. This definition of income diversification is linked to the concept of structural transformation at the national level, defined as the long term decline in the percentage contribution of agriculture sector to gross domestic product (GDP) and employment in growing economies.

Income diversification can also be defined as the process of switching from low value crop production to higher value crops, livestock, and off-farm activities. Thus, many analysis of income consider income diversification as strategies employed to earn cash income in addition to primary production activities from a variety of sources (Dercon & Krishnan, 1996). The United Kingdom Department of Foreign and International Development (DFID) (2004) incorporate “a livelihood” which comprises the capabilities, assets and activities required for a means of living. Livelihood diversification thus, refers to attempts by individuals and households to find new ways to raise income and reduce risk, which differ by the freedom of choice. Livelihood diversification includes both on-farm and off-farm activities which are undertaken to generate income additional to that from the main household agricultural activities, via the production of other agricultural and nonagricultural goods and services, the sale of wage labor or self-employment and other strategies to spread risk (Oluwatayo, 2009).

2.2. Effects of Off-Farm Income Diversification

The importance of income diversification on household income has been widely documented. For example, Reardon’s (1997) review of several case studies in Africa found a strong positive

relationship between the off-farm income share and total household income levels in most situations, though there are differences in what exactly constitutes off-farm income across the different studies. Similarly, Abdulai and Delgado (1999) and Reardon et al. (1992) have shown that off-farm income diversification is associated with higher overall household income. Barrett, Bezuneh and Aboud (2001) reported a strong association between greater income diversification and total income in Kenya and Cote d'Ivoire.

In rural Mexico, de Janvry and Sadoulet (2001) found that participation in off-farm activities helps to reduce poverty and to increase household incomes. In terms of agricultural production, Collier and Lar (1986) found a significant relationship between off-farm income and crop output in rural Kenya, after controlling for production inputs. In terms of food security, Reardon, et al. (1992) found that income diversification into the off-farm sector improves daily per adult equivalent calorie consumption in the Sahelian and Guinean agro ecological zones of Burkina Faso. Tschirley and Weber (1994) showed that off-farm income has a small but positive effect on calorie availability among rural households in Angoche district of Northern Zimbabwe. By using the 24-hour consumption recall data, the study found that a 1% increase in off-farm income would increase calorie availability by 0.04%.

Also in Zimbabwe, Ersado (2003) found that off-farm income diversification is associated with a higher level of consumption expenditure in rural areas, following the economic policy change and drought of the early 1990s. Similarly, Ruben and van den Berg (2001) demonstrated that calorie intake adequacy is strongly enhanced through engagement in off-farm activities among rural households in Honduras. The study also showed that off-farm income has a positive effect on the use of external farm inputs in agricultural production, directly affecting household food availability and consumption. Evidence on the effects of off-farm income diversification on income inequality is mixed. Studies by van den Berg and Kumbi (2006) in Ethiopia and by Lanjouw (1998) in Ecuador indicate that off-farm activities reduce rural inequality, while Reardon (1997) found that off-farm income contributes to increasing inequality in several African countries.

2.3. Determinants of Off-Farm Income Diversification

Similar to the importance of off-farm income for total income, analysis of the determinants of off-farm income diversification has received considerable attention in the literature. Davis and Bezemer (2004) maintain that the decision to participate in off-farm activities generally depends

on two main factors, namely: - a) The capacity/ability to participate, and b) The motivation to participate. Household's capacity to undertake off-farm activities is usually a function of factors such as education, age, gender, income, assets, access to credit. In a literature review, Barrett, Reardon and Webb (2001) found a strong positive relationship between education and off-farm income in almost all of the papers reviewed.

Similarly, studies by de Janvry and Sadoulet (2001) in Mexico and by Ruben and van den Berg (2001) in Honduras observed that education plays a major role in accessing better remunerated off-farm employment activities. Some studies have also reported a differential effect of education on income activities. For instance, a study by Taylor and Yunez-Naude (2000) in Mexico found high returns to schooling in wage labor, whereas the returns in the production of staples are low and not significant. In Uganda, secondary school education was identified as a pre-requisite for wage employment in the government and NGO sectors (Cannon and Smith, 2002). Some evidence has also shown that household assets are important for off-farm income diversification.

In the African context Reardon (1997) showed that household wealth has a positive relation with income from off-farm sources. In Burkina Faso, Reardon, Delgado and Matlon (1992) found that prior wealth is important for income diversification. Similarly, Kinsey et al (1998) showed a positive and significant relation between household wealth and off-farm income diversification in rural Zimbabwe. Reardon (1997, p.8) emphasizes the important of household assets by submitting that, "given the underdeveloped credit markets to finance off-farm businesses, own-cash sources are important to start off-farm enterprises and pay for transaction costs to obtain off-farm employment". Other than household assets, physical infrastructure such as road, electricity, water, telecommunication etc. were shown to be important for rural off-farm income diversification. For example, a study by Corral and Reardon (2001) in Nicaragua found that road access, as well as access to electricity and water, is important for off-farm incomes.

Also, Escobal (2001) showed that in rural Peru access to public assets such as roads can help rural households to increase their self employment as well as wage employment in the off-farm sector. The importance of physical infrastructure emanates from the fact that it facilitates the starting of an own business as well as taking up off-farm employment by reducing transportation and transaction costs. In addition to the correlates of off-farm income diversification discussed so far, the literature has also identified the importance of access to market, family size and composition,

and gender for participation in the off-farm sector of the rural economy. For instance, studies by Canagarajah et al. (2001) in Tanzania and Smith et al. (2001) in Uganda showed that better physical access to markets increases off-farm earnings. Similarly, Lanjouw et al. (2001) showed that better access to the market is important for participation in the off-farm sector in the peri-urban areas of Tanzania. Reardon (1997) stated that family size and structure affect the ability of the household to supply labor to the off-farm sector.

Studies by Reardon, Delgado and Matlon (1992) in Burkina Faso and Clay et al. (1995) in Rwanda found that larger and polygamous families supplied more labor to the rural off-farm labor market. This allows some wives to assume home maintenance activities and the labor surplus to work off-farm. In contrast, the relationship between gender and participation in off-farm activities does not show a clear trend across studies. For example, Newman and Canagarajah (1999) found that in rural Uganda men participate more in off-farm activities than women. The study revealed that men show greater propensity to diversify into off-farm traditional occupations such as carpentry and construction. On the other hand, Berdegue et al. (2001) found that women in Chile tend to gravitate more towards off-farm employment than their men counterparts.

2.4. Analyzing and Measuring Off-Farm Income Diversification

Two commonly used methods of analyzing off-farm income diversification can be identified in the literature (Brown et al., 2006). The first method is the **income-based approach**, which looks at household participation and income earned from the different off-farm activities of the rural economy. For instance, Barrett et al. (2005) analyzed the relationship between total income and the proportion of income earned in farm and off-farm activities in three African countries, noting how these proportions changed across income quartiles and that different income sources became dominant as one moved up the income distribution. Some studies have also classified the available diversification strategies into distinct groups and examine the income as well as the factors involved in rural household's choice of any particular strategy (Damite and Negatu, 2004; Barrett, Bezuneh and Aboud, 2001).

The second method is the **asset-based approach**, which analyzes the income diversification behavior of rural households by direct examination of the household's asset endowment (Carter and Barrett, 2006; Brown et al., 2006). Several methods have also been reported in the literature for measuring the degree of income diversification. The most common and simplest measure is **the**

number of income sources that a household has. Thus, a household with two income sources would be considered more diversified than another household with just one income source (Ersado, 2003). This method has been criticized for its arbitrariness. In particular, it has been argued that a household with more economically active adults, other things being equal, will be more likely to have more income sources. This may reflect household labor supply decisions as much as a desire for diversification. Second, it may be argued that there is discrepancy when comparing households receiving different shares of their income from similar activities. For instance, a household obtaining 99% of its income from farming and 1% from wage labor has the same number of income sources as a household with 50% from farming and 50% from wage labor, if appropriate corrections are not made.

The advantage of this method, however, is that it is easy to measure and also allows studying income diversification behavior in urban areas, thus facilitating an urban-rural comparison. A second method of measuring income diversification is the share of off-farm income in total income. The assumption here is that a higher share of off-farm income amounts to higher diversification from the farm into the off-farm sector and lower vulnerability to weather related shocks, which is one of the main risk factors confronting farm households. The major disadvantage of this method is that it is difficult to measure, because it requires accurate accounting of incomes from farm and off-farm sources. It also has less relevance in urban areas, since most of the urban incomes are based on off-farm activities (Ersado, 2005).

A third measure of income diversification is the Herfindahl index (Barrett and Reardon, 2000). This index measures the overall diversity in income and takes into account the variations in the income shares from different sources. It measures the degree of concentration of household income. Accordingly, households with most diversified incomes will have the smallest Herfindahl index, while those with less diversified incomes will have larger values. For the least diversified households (i.e., those depending on only one single income source), the Herfindahl index takes on its maximum value of one. It should be noted that there are also other measures of income diversification, such as the share of income from high-value crops or the share of crop output that is sold commercially. These, however, are not considered in this particular study.

2.2. Empirical Literature Review

In this section some studies that deal with off-farm or off-farm employment participation decision and earnings from those activities are reviewed. Mostly the question, why do rural households diversify their livelihoods arises on livelihood studies. Barrett and Reardon (2000) have attempted to answer for this question on their study of income diversification and household livelihood diversification strategies in rural Africa. They stated that farm household diversification in to off-farm activities emerge from diminishing or time-varying returns to factors of production, from market failures (e.g. for credit) or frictions (e.g. for mobility or entry into high-return niches), from ex ante risk management, and from ex post coping with adverse shocks.

Where returns to productive assets (e.g. land, labor or livestock) vary across time or among individuals within a household or households within a community, individuals, or households will diversify their assets, activities and incomes. In addition, incomplete markets (e.g. for land, labor, credit, or insurance) may induce farm households to diversify their livelihood. For example, a smallholder household endowed with much labor but relatively little land will in the absence of well-functioning land markets hence apply some labor to its own farm and hire some labor out for off-farm wage employment in agriculture. Because when individuals or households are not endowed with the ratio that maximizes returns and there are not well-developed asset markets through which they can exchange assets to achieve the optimal mix, diversification becomes the usual response.

Similarly, where markets for credit or insurance are incomplete, individuals are typically unable to smooth consumption even they desire credit to smooth the production or income variability. For many institutional, infrastructural, technological, and informational reasons, financial markets are usually incomplete in rural Africa. So, individuals must act outside of financial markets in order to reduce consumption variability driven by real income variability. Diversification is a primary means by which many individuals reduce risk (Barrett et.al, 2001). On the contrary, missing markets can discourage diversification. According to Reardon 1997 missing credit markets can hinder diversification into activities or assets characterized by substantial barriers to entry (as cited in Reardon et al., 2001).

On the other hand, if off-farm options can be accessed easily, but credit markets are incomplete, off-farm earnings can be a crucial means for overcoming working capital constraints to purchasing necessary variable inputs for farming (e.g. fertilizer, seeds, equipment, labor) or to make capital improvements (e.g. bunds, ridges, irrigation) to one's farm (Woldehanna & Oskam, 2001). Diversification also serves as a coping response for ex post shocks. When crops fail or livestock die, households must reallocate labor to other pursuits, whether formal off-farm employment (e.g. wage labor), informal off-farm employment (e.g. hunting), or non agricultural activities (e.g. weaving and brewing). One implication of diversification as risk management rationale is that the need for self-insurance is a function of the availability of substitute social insurance, provided through transfers by the government, by non-profit organizations, by community or family members.

Since social insurance can at least partly substitute for self insurance, one would expect greater need for asset, activity, and income diversification where social insurance is relatively scarce. This might be indicated by the high dependence of African farm households on off-farm income, as governments, communities, and relief agencies offer meager and frequently slow safety nets, and the social foundations of traditional safety nets appears to be stretched (Barrett et.al, 2001; Ellis, 2000). De Janvry and Sadoulet (2001) have used a multinomial estimation to analyze the determinants of participation in off-farm activities using Mexican ejido level data. They documented that the effect of individual characteristics, for instance, the presence of adult males of less than 35 years old have higher probability of participation in off-farm activities than do the household heads. Females at all age levels have lower probability participation in off-farm activities than the head of the household.

In the same study, regarding the effect of education, they found that households with 9 or more average years of schooling have higher likelihood of participation over those with less than three years. Greater access to land and ethnicity (defined as speaking indigenous language) reduces participation in off-farm wage work. Location, defined as the number of urban centers within one hour of travel by public transport makes no difference across all individuals, but increases females participation in non agricultural wage labor while decreasing participation in agricultural wage labor. They also reported that low access of land, human capital, migration assets and ethnicity play negative role on non-agricultural income. Atamanov (2011) on his study made in Kyrgyz

republic has tried to identify the determinants of individual participation in pure off-farm and a mixture of farm and off-farm activities based on a multinomial logit regression analysis (where pure agricultural activities is the choice comparison). Results show that push factors like availability of small land size and poor land quality make individuals choose off-farm activities over agricultural activities. The negative influence of age of the household head and number cattle are also an indication of push factors.

But, he found also some indication of pull factors, for example, the marginal increase in land owned by the household (denoted by land owned square), decreases probability of participation in off-farm activities at a decreasing rate, indicating that there may be less incentive for those with ample access for land to divert from off-farm activities. The study tries also to show the determinants of participation off-farm activities by disaggregating in to self-employment, employment by private organizations, public organizations and by individuals. Gender has different effect across the off-farm activities. Women are likely to engage in public off-farm organizations, while men are more likely to employ by private organizations and individuals. Education is found to have a significant effect to be employed by public and private organizations unlike for self-employment and employment by individuals.

He tried also to estimate the determinants of off-farm earnings using double hurdle model for the participant households. Age increases the level of off-farm earnings from public and private organizations but doesn't affect the level of income from self-employment. Males reap high-income from both wage and self-employment activities than their female counterparts. Education positively affects off-farm income, even for self-employment income, where education does not affect participation in self-employment. Access to infrastructure and market characteristics also increases level of earning from wage and self-employment activities. Asset ownership in the form of livestock increases significantly earnings from off-farm activities.

Ibekwe, Eze, Ohajianya, Orebiyi, Onyemauwa, and Korie (2010) have reported a result that supports the distress diversification hypothesis, for they found a negative relationship between off-farm-income and the farm output per hectare of land using a survey data from south east Nigeria. The study tries also to show the effect of other variables like education, age of the household head, farm size, household size and farm investment. Education of the head has positive and significant effect on the level of off-farm income at 5% significant level. The variables like farm size,

household size and farm investment have a negative and significant correlation with off-farm income. The coefficient for age of the household head was not significant and negatively correlated with off-farm income. Regarding to the income diversification of the farm households, studies found that the existence of substantial entry or mobility barriers (particularly in labor market and financial and credit) to high return niches within off-farm economy make the poor to have less diversified asset and income portfolio and enter only into less remunerative activities (Barrett, Bezuneh, & Aboud, 2001; Barrett & Reardon, 2000).

Barrett et al (2001) has extended and explains the difference in income portfolios and livelihood diversification pattern are associated with labor market segmentation, barrier to entry, location and potential income growth. Oluwatayo (2009) has made similar study on poverty and income diversification among households in rural Nigeria. Tobit regression model has used to show the determinants of livelihood diversification. Male headed, small sized family, non-poor households with formal education and better income and access to credit facility were affect the livelihood index positively. Besides, Determinants of income share from different sources of off-farm activities among rural households in the same country has explored by other group of researchers (Olugbenga, Adewunmi, John & Adebayo, 2011). The study indicates that education, experience in any off-farm activity and distance to urban center were the major determinants of income shares from different sources of off-farm activities.

Evidence from rural areas of Tanzania shows the determinants of off-farm wage work participation(defined by the number of households who supply labor to the rural local market) and share of labor income in total cash income (Muduma & Wobst,2005). The study finds that education level, availability of land, access to economic centers and credit are the most important factors in determining the number of households that participate in a particular rural local labor market and share of labor income in total cash income. The factors that influence labor supply, labor demand and household members' choice between farm and off-farm work were also determined among smallholder farmers in three regions of southern Uganda (Bagamba, Burger & Kuyvenhoven, 2007).

Results on the time allocation decisions revealed that farm size had a significant negative effect on the amount of labor supplied to off-farm work; which is consistent with the assertion that farmers seek off-farm employment due to push factors .The results also confirmed that factors such as

education and road access, which improve the opportunity cost of labor in the off-farm sector, affect positively the amount of time allocated in off-farm activities. This implies that investment in education and road infrastructure would favor the off-farm sector against on-farm employment. Men would benefit most from development of the off-farm sector, as most of the household individuals employed in the sector are men.

Freese (2010) has documented finding from Burkina Faso which are consistent to the results found from other sub-Saharan African countries. The empirical paper uses Heckman two-step selection model to determine the probability of participation and level of income generated in the off-farm sector. The regressions are applied to the pooled data, as well as the wealthiest and poorest expenditure quintiles respectively. The result shows having male headed households and more adult male members decreases the probability of participation in non-farm sector for the poorest quintiles. Household size increases the likelihood to participate in the off-farm sector for the pooled data. Education variables influence participation positively for the pooled data and wealthiest households as well. Interestingly, education of the household head does not affect significantly participation in off-farm sector for the poorest quintiles.

Moreover, distance to local public infrastructure (as measured by distance to secondary school, health center and market) negatively significantly affects participation. The analysis shows also education and proximity to community structure positively and significantly affects income from off-farm activities for the wealthier quintile and pool data. For the poorest households only, distance to health centers, household age and number of adults influence the success in off-farm earnings. Lanjouw and Murgai (2008), were analyzed the role of agricultural wages and off-farm employment using a panel data in India. According to this literature expansion of the off-farm sector is associated with falling poverty in two ways: a direct impact on poverty that is, likely due to a pro-poor marginal incidence of off-farm employment expansion; and an indirect impact attributable to the positive effect of non-farm employment growth on agricultural wages.

The recent literature on off-farm labor market participation by Babatunde and Matin (2010) in rural Nigeria have described the composition of average household income. It tries also to analyze the determinants of participation in off-farm labor employment and incomes from them. The literature shows 50 percent of household income is derived from off-farm sources. Off-farm self-employment and non-agricultural wage employment accounts 25% and 6% of total household

income respectively. They applied multivariate probit model to estimate the determinants of participation in different off-farm employment activities. Education of both the household head and other adults, availability agricultural and non-agricultural machinery, access to electricity and water and households headed by male positively and significantly affects off-farm employment participation. Distance to market and family size on the other hand significantly hinders participation.

The results from the multivariate probit model indicate that households headed by male have high probability of participation in agricultural and non-agricultural wage employment but is insignificant for self employment. Education of the household head and other adults, positively affects off-farm wage and self-employment activities. But, agricultural wage negatively and significantly affected by education of other adults. Household assets, access to electricity and pipe water encourage self-employment, where as market distance affects negatively. Farm size does not show any significant effect across all off-farm activities. Tobit model has been used to estimate the determinants of income from off-farm involvement. The result indicates family size and land size have positive effect on the level of off-farm income. Exceptional negative effect of family size is reported for self-employed and remittance incomes.

2.2. Empirical Literature from Ethiopia case study

Evidence from Tigray implies participation in off-farm work uses both as ex ante and ex post strategy to reduce household's income variability which a raise from variation and shortage of rain fall (Nigisti, 2007). The finding of her literature shows that household wealth denoted by the value of large livestock and amount of cultivated land negatively affects off-farm work participation. Age of household head and family size significantly influences participation, but the effect for education and labor saving technology proxy by price of pesticides and herbicides has found insignificant. Similarly Bezabih et al., (2010) have also documented the determinants of off-farm employment and activity choice between agriculture and three other off-farm activities in Amhara regional state, Ethiopia using a two year panel data. They found that amount of rain fall decreases participation in off-farm work but the variability in rain fall promotes participation. This is in line with the argument that off-farm employment serves as agricultural risk mitigation strategy. The result shows households with large male and female labor participate more in off-farm

employment. But older household heads are less likely to participate. Presence too large or no land motivates off-farm participation. Ownership of livestock has also a significant and positive effect on the likelihood of households of off-farm employment participation.

Berg and Kumbi (2006) have used a multivariate probit model to estimate the relation between poverty and participation in off-farm sector in Oromia region, Ethiopia. Off-farm activities were disaggregated in to three: hand crafts, food and drink and trade. Their result indicates, own cultivated land, which represents for rural households productive asset has a negative and significant effect on participation across the three off-farm activities. This implies the relatively poor households are more likely to be engaged in off-farm sector. Households owning more pack animals are likely to participate in off-farm activities.

In the same study, a Positive and significant effect of family size and negative effect of dependency ratio on the likelihood of taking part in food/drink activities shows that off-farm activities are used surplus labor from agriculture. Age, experience and primary education positively affects participation in hand craft. While informal education affects positively participation in food/drink and trade. The effect of distance to all weather roads is positive for handcrafts and negative for food/drink. The justification is strong competent from urban areas may reach it easily if roads are accessible for handcrafts, but for local drinks/food may not be interested to supply their commodity to the rural centers using the opportunity of all weather roads. The positive and significant effect of female adult ratio in food/drink implies the traditional female domination of the activities in Oromia region or largely in Ethiopia.

Woldehanna and Oskam (2001) have also made deep study in northern Ethiopia, Tigray on the paper titled "Economic Analysis and Policy Implication of Farm and Off-farm Employment". The literature tries to answer some questions among these I present here what I believe it could be in line with my study. Farmers engage in different off-farm activities to diversify their income and enable them to feed themselves during crop failure, but the main worry is whether it is possible to support farmers to enable them participate without scarifying the farm productivity. To address this problem they analyze the link between farm and off-farm activities and their determinants. Eventually they found a substantial increase of farm income as a result of income diversification in general and promoting off-farm employment in particular. This may because off-farm income helps

to finance farming activities such as purchase of farm labor and other inputs such as seeds, fertilizer and pesticides.

Still there are contradictory hypothesis regarding off-farm employment that on the one hand it produce more cash and on the other hand less labor to be employed on the farm. But the evidence implies the positive impact of off -farm employment on farm productivity outweighs than its compromising effect. This is because one if labor was unemployed/under employed on farm off-farm employment may have no effect on farming, second farmers can make crop choice go friendly with off -farm work and thirdly if the marginal productivity of labor off-farm is better than on their farm still they can hire labor on their farm and supply their labor off-farm.

Reardon 1977 confirmed that, if there are entry barriers and rationing in the labor market, diversifying income in to off-farm activities will be more difficult for poor than for rich households (cited in Reardon, 2001). Hence, it is important to examine the determinants of participation and take mitigation measures. The result shows off-farm wage employment decreases and off-farm self employment increases with an increase of farm output. Other variables that affect off-farm employment are number of dependents, family size, wage, area of land cultivated, livestock wealth and the value of off-farm equipment owned. It increases with family size, wage and livestock wealth and decrease with number of dependents, land cultivated and non-labor income. Hagos and Holden (2003) have examined the welfare impacts of credit access and program participation measured by changes in household's per capita expenditure, the change in household's level of off-farm income over time and others. They found significantly positive impact of credit on the level of off-farm income among households located in tabias that are close to major markets.

2.3. Conceptual Frame Work

The literatures provide us ample evidences in favor of the explanations for farm households' motivations to diversify their incomes and its effect on their economic wellbeing. Based on the above empirical review, we present the conceptual framework that tries to link the major factors that are expected to determine household's decision to participate in off-farm activities and its effect on farmers' economic wellbeing's' below. These factors can be shown by categorizing as factors that influence relative returns to agricultural production and related risks, referred as incentives, and factors that affect the household's capacity of participation in different off-farm

activities (Reardon et al., 2001). Incentives allow farm households to participate in farm and off-farm wage employment, off-farm self employment and social and community service activities to generate incomes. While the factors that limit the capacity of households to participate in off-farm work includes such as education, access to credit and age. Involvement of rural farm households in either farm activities or both farm and off-farm activities will increase the households' income and hence increases HHs consumption expenditure and improving their food security status. The conceptual framework, which established as a foundation for the factors that determine off-farm employment participation and income is presented in the figure below.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework for the determinants of rural households' off-farm income diversification and effect on their economic wellbeing's

Chapter three

3. Methodology

3.1. Profile of the Study Area

The study will conduct in Shebel Berenta and Dejen district, East Gojjam zone, Amhara regional state. According to the traditional climate zone classification, two major vertically stratified temperature zones are found in the districts. These are Woina Dega (sub tropical) and Kolla (tropical) having elevation 1500-2500m and 1000-1500m respectively. The altitude of the study area ranges from 776 meters to 2220 meters above sea level. Small scale mixed agriculture is the dominant source of livelihood to the local people in the districts. As well, Maize, Barely, Wheat, and Teff are the principal crops, and from the livestock cattle, sheep and Goats are the dominant animals in the districts. Moreover, cultivation is done only in one season and during the agricultural peak season people involved in agricultural activities was highly engaged in laborious farm activities. But during off-season they search for alternative employment opportunities in both rural and urban areas. Meanwhile more and more emerging off-farm activities are coming up in Shebel Berenta and Dejen district with increase in urbanization, diminishing agricultural productivity, and growing infrastructure which are creating avenues of off-farm employment.

3.2. Data Types and Sources

The major research method that we have used in the study was a cross-sectional field survey which will supplement by key informant interviews, an extensive literature review and formal preliminary group discussions. The data that was collected for study under consideration may be classified under the following four categories:

- i. Household socio-economic characteristics. These data is allowing us for the analysis of non-income poverty within the survey population, and is collect from both households that have involved in off-farm activities and those that have not. The data includes demographic variables (sex, age, marital status, education and migration of respondents), housing data, ownership of productive resources such as land and working tools, and ownership of livestock.
- ii. Household income. This dataset include household earnings from economic activities, which, in turn, include earnings from self-employment and wage employment in a one-year reference period. Income earned from farm and off-farm activities and other sources will separate. This

set of data is allowing us for the analysis of income poverty among households participating and those not participating in off-farm economic activities.

- iii. Household expenditure. Data was collected on items on which household income earned from the different sources was used. This assists further analysis on the contribution of off-farm activities to household economic well-being.
- iv. Factors determining whether household members participate in farm and off-farm activities, and the performance of these activities. These data includes the skills, knowledge and initial capital require for engaging in particular economic activities. Information was gathers on the type of economic activities undertaken and ability of households to access financial and product markets.

3.3. Sampling Design

Samples were drawn by following a multi-stage sampling technique using both purposive and random methods of sampling. The stages that were involved in the selections are:

Stage 1: This involved the purposive selection of two districts from all districts in East Gojjam Zone. These districts were Shebel Berenta and Dejen Woredas. The selection of two districts as the study area was based on two facts. First, these districts are characterized by low agricultural production levels with erratic rainfall; thus, rural off-farm activities are important economic activities for participating households. Second, these districts are one of the areas with high poverty levels in East Gojjam Zone. Moreover, Dejen district is located along the main road to capital city while Shebel Berenta is located far from the main road. In this way, the study sought to capture the influence of accessibility and transportation to and from the markets on the levels of participation in off-farm activity and performance of off-farm activities in the two districts.

Stage 2: From the two purposively selected districts, three agricultural zones each were purposively selected to give a total of eight (8) agricultural zones.

Stage 3: From the eight (8) agricultural zones that were selected, two Blocks were randomly selected to give a total of 16 Blocks.

Stage 4: From each of the randomly selected sixteen (16) Blocks, two (2) circles were randomly selected to give a total of thirty (32) circles.

Stage 5: From the randomly selected 32 circles, twenty (20) farming households each were randomly selected. Thus, a total of 640 farming households were used as the sample size for the

study. Households who has select in the survey include those that are participating and those not participating in off-farm activities.

3.4. Methods of Data Collection

Data collection for this study was involved in three major methods: a document review, interviews and discussions with key informants. Household interviews in this study were administered using a semi-structured questionnaire, while interviews with key informants were conducted using an unstructured, open-ended checklist. A document review was also used to collect secondary data. The documents read included books, journals, manuscripts, and research and official reports.

3.5. Method of Data Analysis

Data compilation and processing was started immediately after field work. Data processing involved editing, coding, classifying and entering data by using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and STATA. Quantitative and qualitative data were generated and presented via frequencies, and descriptive and multi-response statistics in SPSS. Inferential statistics was also present to scrutinize the effect of rural off-farm activities on households' economic wellbeing's.

3.6. Empirical framework

3.6.1. Modeling Off-farm Activity Participation

A farm household's decision to either participates in off-farm work or not is assumed to be the outcome of a vector of factors related to the farmers' resources and constraints. As noted by, a positive number of off-farm hours will be observed for an individual if the potential market wage is greater than the reservation wage. However, these differential wages are not observable. What is observed is the decision to participate, or not to participate in off-farm work. This study postulates that a farm household will only engage in off-farm work when it gains extra income to complement its farm income (reservation wage). The study begins by observing participating and non-participating households, as to whether they differ significantly in terms of household characteristics, farm characteristics and assets. Thus, Logistic regression model is employed to estimate the determinants of off-farm work participation and to generate estimates for propensity scores. Based on theoretical and empirical considerations, we specify the following model for non-farm employment participation:

$$\begin{aligned}
I_i^* &= \alpha Z_i + v_i \dots\dots\dots (1) \\
I_i &= 1 \quad \text{if } I_i^* > 0 \\
I_i &= 0 \quad \text{otherwise}
\end{aligned}$$

where I_i^* is the probability that a farm household works off-farm in addition to its primary farm work (also known as the latent variable), which is observed through the choice to participate in off-farm work. The observed dichotomous choice to work off-farm is given by I_i , which is equal to 1 for a farm household that engages in at least one off-farm work activity and 0 for a farm household that does not engage in any off-farm work activities. α is the vector of parameters to be estimated, and v is the error term under the assumption that $v \sim N(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{1})$. Z includes household characteristics, farm characteristics, agro-ecological risks and public transportation condition, which are expected to determine the likelihood of engaging in off-farm activities.

3.6.2. Modeling the effects of off-farm participation on household food consumption

According to the standard agricultural household model, a farm household allocates labor and consumption levels by maximizing the utility subject to cash and production technology constraints. Because it generates additional income, participation in off-farm activities is very likely to determine household economic-wellbeing. This study hypothesizes that participation in off-farm activities exerts positive effects on household economic-wellbeing because it increases household earnings and consumptions. To assess the effects of off-farm engagement on household economic-wellbeing, a commonly used model in the literature on effect evaluation is written as follows:

$$Y = \beta X + \gamma I + \varepsilon \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

where Y is the household's per capita food consumption expenditure and food availability; X includes household and farm characteristics and other factors, which are expected to affect the consumption expenditure; I is a dummy for participation in off-farm activities; and γ is the coefficient capturing the effects of off-farm participation on the consumption expenditure. However, this coefficient may be biased and inconsistent due to the self-selection of farm households into the off-farm participant group. If, for example, participants are wealthier or live in an area with a high cost of living, their expenditure on food consumption is higher, irrespective of whether they participate in off-farm activities. As well, the farm households' off-farm skills and

motivation for diversifying household earnings can also influence both their decisions of whether to participate or not participate in off-farm activities and household food consumption levels. The coefficient on the off-farm dummy (I) would, in this case, also include the effects of these unobserved factors and, thus, produce an overestimate of the effects of off-farm activities. In econometrics, when unobserved effects are correlated with both the regressed (per capita food consumption and food availability) and a regressor (off-farm participation), the coefficient on the latter is inconsistent and biased.

One can use a Heckman selection approach or standard treatment effect model to control for this selection bias. Still, these approaches cannot control for the potential systematic differences between the groups due to the assumption that the consumption functions differ between the participants and nonparticipants by only a constant term. As well Holden (2003) adopted the propensity score matching approach that can account for the systematic differences in observed characteristics. This approach may still yield biased and inconsistent estimates because it cannot control for unobserved factors that potentially affect both the decision of whether to engage in off-farm activities and the consumption expenditure.

The endogenous switching model is adopted to address the above-mentioned econometric challenges. The model treats participation in off-farm activities and nonparticipation as regimes and is specified as follows:

$$I = \alpha Z + v \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

$$y_1 = \beta_1 X_1 + u_1 \text{ if } I^* = 1 \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

$$y_0 = \beta_0 X_0 + u_0 \text{ if } I^* = 0 \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

where y_1 and y_0 represent household expenditure on food consumption per capita for off-farm participants and nonparticipants, respectively; I is a latent variable, as defined in Equation (1); and α , β_1 and β_0 are vectors of parameters to be estimated. v , u_1 and u_0 are error terms that are contemporaneously correlated and assumed to be jointly normally distributed with a zero mean vector and the following covariance matrix:

$$\text{cov}(v, u_1, u_0) = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{u_1}^2 & \sigma_{u_1 u_0} & \sigma_{u_1 v} \\ \sigma_{u_1 u_0} & \sigma_{u_0}^2 & \sigma_{u_0 v} \\ \sigma_{u_1 v} & \sigma_{u_0 v} & \sigma_v^2 \end{bmatrix} \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

When there are unobserved effects, the error term v of the selection equation is correlated with the error terms u_1 and u_0 of the outcome equations. That is, the expected values of u_1 and u_0 would be nonzero conditional on regime selection. Therefore, endogeneity can be tested with estimates of the covariance terms $\sigma_{u_1 v}$ and $\sigma_{u_0 v}$. If $\sigma_{u_1 v} = \sigma_{u_0 v} = \mathbf{0}$, the model exhibits exogenous switching; if either $\sigma_{u_1 v}$ or $\sigma_{u_0 v}$ is nonzero, the model shows endogenous switching. In this case, one needs to test for significant coefficients of the correlation between u_1 and v ($\rho_{u_1 v} = \sigma_{u_1 v} / \sigma_{u_1} \sigma_v$) and between u_0 and v ($\rho_{u_0 v} = \sigma_{u_0 v} / \sigma_{u_0} \sigma_v$). Using these correlations, the expected values of the error terms u_1 and u_0 conditional on regime selection can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} E(u_1 | I = 1, X_1) &= E(u_1 | v) - \alpha Z = \sigma_{u_1 v} \frac{\phi(Z\alpha)}{\Phi(Z\alpha)} \\ &= \sigma_{u_1 v} \lambda_1 \dots\dots\dots (7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} E(u_0 | I = 0, X_0) &= E(u_0 | v \leq -\alpha Z) = \sigma_{u_0 v} \frac{-\phi(Z\alpha)}{1 - \Phi(Z\alpha)} \\ &= \sigma_{u_0 v} \lambda_0 \dots\dots\dots (8) \end{aligned}$$

where ϕ is the standard normal probability density function and Φ is the cumulative distribution function of the standard normal distribution. λ_1 and λ_0 are the Inverse Mills Ratios (IMRs) predicted at $Z\alpha$ for participants and nonparticipants, respectively.

In addition to the endogeneity test, $\rho_{u_1 v}$ and $\rho_{u_0 v}$ allow economic interpretations based on their signs. If the coefficients $\rho_{u_1 v}$ and $\rho_{u_0 v}$ have opposite signs, farmers decide whether to participate in off-farm activities based on the comparative advantage. That is, participants enjoy above-average consumption levels once they participate in off-farm activities if $\rho_{u_1 v} < \mathbf{0}$, whereas nonparticipants enjoy above-average consumption levels when they do not participate if $\rho_{u_0 v} > \mathbf{0}$. Alternately, if $\rho_{u_1 v}$ and $\rho_{u_0 v}$ have the same signs, ‘hierarchical sorting’ is evidenced, suggesting that the participants consume above-average levels regardless of whether they participate in off-farm activities but they are better off participating than not participating. Similarly, the nonparticipants consume below-average levels in either case but they are better off

choosing not to participate in off-farm activities. Furthermore, the coefficients ρ_{u_1v} and ρ_{u_0v} can indicate model consistency under the condition $\rho_{u_1v} < \rho_{u_0v}$. This condition also implies that the participants' consumption levels are above what they otherwise would be if they did not participate in off-farm activities.

3.6.3. Estimation approach

Once either σ_{u_1v} or σ_{u_0v} takes a nonzero value, one can estimate the model by using a two-stage procedure. In the first stage, a logit model of regime choice is estimated, providing the estimates of α , on which the IMRs λ_1 and λ_0 can be predicted according to Equations (7) and (8). Because the endogenous switching regression model resembles a sample selection model, the selection in the first stage is responsible for the selection bias arising from unobserved factors such as wealth, skills and motivation that potentially affect both the farm households' decision to participate in off-farm activities and food consumption levels. Generally, in the selection model, the logit model is estimated because of the assumption that the error term v is normally distributed with a zero mean and variance σ_v^2 normalized to 1.

In the second stage, the outcome equations are estimated by including the predicted IMRs as regressors. The estimated coefficients of IMRs yield the estimates of σ_{u_1v} and σ_{u_0v} . However, due to the estimation of the IMRs, the residuals u_1 and u_0 cannot be employed to compute the standard errors of estimates in the second stage. Simultaneously estimating the selection and outcome equations with the full information maximum likelihood (FIML) procedure is more efficient for the endogenous switching regression. Because the endogenous switching model resembles a sample selection model, it should be noted that the coefficients β_1 and β_0 in Equations (4) and (5) measure the marginal effects of explanatory variables on household food consumption unconditional on households' actual regime choice. That is, the effects of X on the respective subsample y (y_1 for participant group or y_0 for nonparticipant group).

3.6.4. Estimation of effects of off-farm participation on household food consumption

The particular interest of the current study is to quantify the effects of off-farm activities on farm household food consumption expenditure and food availability. To do this, one needs to compare the participants' conditional expected consumption derived from the endogenous switching

regression model with the counterfactual case that the same participants have chosen not to participate. The conditional expected value of food consumption expenditure and food availability by a farm household with characteristics X and Z that participates in off-farm activities is derived as follows:

$$E(y_1|I = 1) = \beta_1 X_1 + \sigma_{u_1 v} \lambda_1 \dots \dots \dots (9)$$

where $\sigma_{u_1 v} \lambda_1$ accounts for sample selection arising from the fact that a farm household participating in off-farm activities differs from other households with characteristics X and Z because of unobserved characteristics. The conditional expected value of food consumption that the same farm household would enjoy without participation is derived from the following:

$$E(y_0|I = 1) = \beta_0 X_1 + \sigma_{u_0 v} \lambda_1 \dots \dots \dots (10)$$

The consumption gain, which is defined as the change in per capita food consumption expenditure and food availability due to off-farm participation, can then be computed as follows:

$$E(y_1|I = 1) - E(y_0|I = 1) = (\beta_1 - \beta_0) X_1 + (\sigma_{u_1 v} - \sigma_{u_0 v}) \lambda_1 \dots \dots \dots (11)$$

In the literature on impact assessment, this consumption gain is called the average treatment effect on the treated (ATT), which accounts for all factors potentially leading to consumption differences. This treatment effect on the treated results from the differences in the coefficients in Equations (9) and (10) ($\beta_1 - \beta_0$ and $\sigma_{u_1 v} - \sigma_{u_0 v}$). If a farm household self-selects to participate in off-farm activities or not participate based on the comparative advantage, $\sigma_{u_1 v} - \sigma_{u_0 v}$ would be positive, and participation in off-farm activities would produce bigger benefits in terms of food consumption expenditure and food availability under self-selection than under random assignment. In this case, a simple comparison between mean consumption in the participant group $E(y_1|I = 1)$ and that in the nonparticipant group $E(y_0|I = 0)$ would result in an upward bias of the treatment effect, which is accounted for in Equation (11).

Chapter Four

4. Results and Discussion of Findings

4.1. Introduction

This chapter deals with the analysis of the survey data and interpretation of the results of data analysis. Results on demographic data and household income are presented first in the form of descriptive statistics where tables, graphs and charts are used to report summary data such as mean, mode, median, central tendency and percentage among others. The empirical results are presented and discussed later in the chapter. The empirical results are used for the answering of research questions i.e. the contribution of off-farm activities in sustaining the livelihood in the study area as well as Constraints of off-farm rural diversification.

4.2. Descriptive Analysis

Demographic characteristics of sampled households

In this section, household heads' demographic characteristics and aspects such as gender, age, family sizes, land size, access to credit, and market, cooperative membership, and highest educational levels attained are discussed. These aspects are important because the main household activities are coordinated by the household head and the head's decisions are most likely to be influenced by such demographic aspects (Makhura, 2001). According to Randela (2005), demographic characteristics of households are essential when analyzing economic data because such factors influence the households' economic behavior. As such, it is relevant to include household demographic attributes in analyzing off-farm participation choices among the smallholder farmers in East Gojjam Zone.

4.2.1. Family size of the respondents

Household size was defined as to the number of people living together in a household including non-family members by Perett (1999). Household size plays an important role as a source of labor; however, the household size also has an impact on household expenditures per month. The mean family size of off-farm diversified and non-diversified households for this study was 7.33 and 4.44 respectively. The largest the family size in the survey comprised 9 members while the smallest family size was 2. The larger the family size, the greater the chances of diversifying livelihood strategies to carter for the needs of the household members (Gebru and Beyene, 2012). In some

cases individual characteristics influence participation decisions. The significance levels (i.e. 2.89) indicate that there is a statistical difference between the two groups with respect family size; it's greater in diversified households than non-diversified one. Moreover, Montshwe (2006) indicated that family size is a useful unit of analysis given the assumptions that within the household resources are pooled, income is shared, and decisions are made jointly by responsible household members. Hence, the smaller the family size the less the livestock sales will be because of fewer family needs that require substantial cash (Obi, 2011). The larger the number of family members employed off-farm, the larger the chances of livelihood diversification strategies of a particular household.

Table 4.1 presents the descriptive of the relevant variables used in the study i.e. Diversified and non-diversified households and also their mean differences. The sample consists of 58% diversified households and 42% non-diversified households that depend solely on farming as means of livelihood from the total 620 samples.

Variable Name	Description	Diversified HHs (58%)		Non-diversified HHs (42%)		Diff. in Means
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Dependent variable						
<i>Off-farm income Diversification</i>	1 if either the household head or any member of the household diversified into off-farm activity, 0 otherwise.					
Outcome Variables						
<i>Consumption Expenditure</i>	Annual household consumption expenditure (in ETH birr).	16,245.64	2402.45	15,273.59	1569.31	972.05***
<i>Food Shortage</i>	1 if household had experienced food shortage in last six months, 0 otherwise.	0.49	0.50	0.24	0.44	0.26**
Independent Variables						
HHs' Characteristics						
<i>Sex</i>	1 if household head is male, 0 otherwise.	1.52	0.50	1.46	0.50	0.06***
<i>Age</i>	Age of household head.	48.0	14.29	50.0	16.30	-2.00***
<i>Age Square</i>	Square of age.	2596	1528	2862	1774	-266***
<i>Health</i>	1 if household head has any form of health disability in last six months, 0 otherwise.	0.30	0.44	0.21	0.41	0.09*
<i>Education</i>	Highest years of formal education of household head	6.13	5.32	4.06	4.61	2.06**
<i>Education Square</i>	Square of education.	37.58	28.30	16.48	21.25	21.1*
HHs' Endowments						
<i>Family Size</i>	Number of household members.	7.33	11.16	4.44	4.13	2.89**
<i>Farm Size</i>	Size of farm in hectares.	1.71	57.4	2.05	42.6	-0.34**
Community level Characteristics						

<i>Mobile phone</i>	1 if household has access to mobile phone services, 0 otherwise.	0.77	0.42	0.69	0.46	0.07
<i>Electricity</i>	1 if household has access to electricity, 0 otherwise.	0.75	0.43	0.56	0.50	0.19***
<i>Transportation</i>	1 if household has access to public transportation, 0 otherwise.	0.97	0.17	0.92	0.27	0.05*
<i>Market</i>	Distance to product market in kilometers.	4.44	4.13	7.33	11.16	-2.89**
<i>Transport*Market</i>	Interaction of access to transport and proximity to market.	1.58	1.93	1.82	2.34	-0.24
Entry Barriers						
<i>Social Capital</i>	1 if household head is a member of any cooperative, 0 otherwise.	0.75	0.44	0.70	0.46	0.05 ***
<i>Formal Credit</i>	1 if household had access to formal credit facility, 0 otherwise	0.33	0.47	0.25	0.44	0.07 **
Location Factor						
<i>Dejen</i>	1 if household lives in Dejen, 0 otherwise.	0.49	0.50	0.24	0.44	0.26***

Source: our computation (2019)

***, ** and * denotes statistical significance at 1%, 5% and 10% levels respectively

4.2.2. Gender of respondents

In this survey 72% of the respondents were male household heads while the rest of the respondents were female. The female headed households included those that were headed by females whose husbands were migrant workers, were deceased or the females that were never married. The households in which husbands were working in other towns were considered female headed as the females would be more involved in day to day livelihood activities. The larger male percentage (72%) may mean greater chances of diversification in households where male household heads access craft and brick facilities as well as hard manual construction jobs in the nearby towns. The significance levels (i.e. 0.06) indicate that there are a statistical differences between the two groups with respect gender composition, male participants was greater in diversified households than the non-diversified one. Gebru and Beyene (2012) in their research related gender to diversification and found out that female households have fewer chances to participate in off-farm activities since they invest much time in domestic roles such as childcare, cooking, washing cloth, gathering fire wood, fetching water with high participation in low economic value and time consuming agricultural activities like weeding and harvesting. Moreover,

as it was discovered by De Brauw *et al.*, (2002) and Shi *et al.*, (2007), there was a clear gender bias in participation into off-farm activities. Men are much more likely to engage in any occupation (local wage employment, local self-employment and migration) rather than in farm labor than are women.

4.2.3. Age of the respondents

The mean age of the respondents both for diversified and non-diversified households' in the survey are presented in Table 4.1 above. Accordingly, the mean age of diversified and non-diversified respondents was 48 and 50 respectively. The survey result indicates that the majority of the respondents (about 86%) are in the Economically Active Population (includes people from 15 to 64 years of age who are either employed or unemployed and seeking employment). Indeed that in this age, individual is most active, able to think quickly, intelligently and have found gainful employment in farming, hence their involvement in different activities and are duty-bound to provide for their household. This may increase the chances of seeking off-farm livelihood strategies, and hence increasing the chances of rural household livelihood diversification. The significance levels (i.e. -2.00) indicate that there are statistical differences between the two groups with respect age composition; the age of participants was less in diversified households than the non-diversified one. Ageing may be one of the factors that reduced the levels of diversification of livelihood strategies in the households of the interviewed population. In general the results implies that diversification of income is common among the young household heads who are more energetic and could afford to take the risks associated with income diversification.

4.2.4. Highest educational attainment of respondents

Education and training are important aspects in rural households as they contribute to the knowledge acquired by households which they can use and apply for improved livelihoods (Bembridge, 1987). Bembridge (1987) went on to indicate that education has long been recognized as a central element in the socio-economic evolution of less developed countries. The education levels of the household heads were assessed for this sample. Table 4.1 above illustrates the levels of education attained by the diversified and non-diversified respondents in the survey. 25 percent of the household heads attained secondary education. This secondary education ranged from grade 8

to grade 12. About 22% of the respondents did not receive any formal education and less than 10% of these respondents attained tertiary education. Hence, about 78% of the respondents acquired at least basic education. The mean educational attainment of diversified and non-diversified households was 6.13 and 4.06 respectively. The significance levels (i.e. 2.06) indicate that there are a statistical differences between the two groups with respect educational attainment, educational levels was greater in diversified households than the non-diversified one. The greater percentage of the households that acquired formal education may result in an increase in the number of chances of diversifying rural household livelihood strategies in the study area. Education increases chances of access to a number of different economic activities, either as a formal requirement for wage earning jobs or because it helps setting up and managing own small businesses (Minot *et al.*, 2006).

4.2.5. Land sizes owned by respondents

The amount of land a farmer owns can be associated with the amount of produce obtained in a season *ceteris paribus*. It should, however, be acknowledged that it is not always the case that the available land will be fully utilized for farming. The average land size owned by diversified and non-diversified households in this sample was 1.71 and 2.05 hectares respectively. Land sizes ranged from 0.25 to 3 hectares per household. The significance levels (i.e. -0.34) indicate that there are a statistical differences between the two groups with respect farm size endowment; farm size was less in diversified households than the non-diversified one. According to Matsumoto *et al.*, (2006), households' access to land, asset endowments, demographic composition and transfers determines the capability to participate in off-farm activities. Land ownership probably is the major constraints that restricted households from owning large animal numbers. This may therefore push households to diversify their livelihood strategies. In areas like Shebel Berenta and Dejen where agriculture is the backbone, households may be restricted to on-farm livelihood strategies if they do not have access to government social grants to diversify their livelihoods'.

4.2.6. Cooperative membership

Membership to cooperatives is a means of building social net-works that enable households to obtain updated information in sharing pooled labour, farm equipment, cash credit usage and

other off-farm income generating activities (Gebru and Beyene, 2012). The results of the survey indicate that, out of the total of 620 sample respondents, 57% were active cooperative members while about 43% of them were no longer willing to participate in some of these cooperatives though all the respondents had equal access to formal and informal cooperative institutions. Here, most of the farm households involved in cooperatives was able to diversify their livelihood strategies into off-farm strategies as they share pooled labor, farm equipment, cash credit usage in their cooperatives. The significance levels (i.e. 0.05) indicate that there are a statistical differences between the two groups with respect cooperative membership; cooperative membership was greater in diversified households than the non-diversified one. Only 4.2% of the members to cooperatives relied solely on on-farm livelihood strategy. About 65% of the members to any cooperatives diversified their livelihood strategies. Therefore, members to cooperatives may have a greater chance of diversifying their livelihood strategies than cooperative non-members who doesn't share cooperative resources.

4.2.7. Market access

Among various social services, access to market plays a crucial role in determining access to assets and livelihood strategies, terms of exchange for assets, and returns to an investment (Bembridge, 1987). So, households that are closer to market centers get several key advantages including access to larger agricultural markets, save their substantial time, incur much lower transport costs and have access to better and more remunerative off-farm activities. The results show that the mean distance between the main market centre of the districts and the sample respondents of diversified and non-diversified was 4.44 and 7.33 km with a minimum of 0.5 km and a maximum of 16 km. The significance levels (i.e. -2.89) indicate that there are statistical differences between the two groups with respect gender composition; access to market was grater in diversified households than the non-diversified one. Households closer to the market centre were able to diversify their livelihood strategies into off-farm livelihood activities as compared to the households that were situated further from the markets. The households that are closer to the markets have greater chances of participating in off-farm activities in closer towns than the households located far away from these markets, hence an increased chance of diversification. Poor road infrastructure and

long distances to market centers in the districts would reduce the chances of households to diversify their livelihood strategies.

4.2.8. Credit access

Credit is an important source of earning future income which plays a vital role in supporting the production and income generating activities of farmers. However, the results of the survey indicate that 57.6% of the households accessed credit while 42.4% of the households could not access credit. 34.8% of the households that could not access credit relied solely on on-farm livelihood strategy. About 5.2% of the households that could access credit were relying mainly on on-farm livelihood strategy while 52.4% of the households were diversifying their livelihood strategies into off-farm activities. The significance levels (i.e. 0.07) indicate that there are a statistical differences between the two groups with respect credit access; credit access was greater in diversified households than the non-diversified one.

Lack of access to credit facilities remains one of the key problems in the study areas to potential diversification into off-farm activities. Some of the main reasons for households' failure to use credit were: lack of knowledge about credit providers, ascribed tight repayment schedules, fear of repayment back due to crop failure because of drought and disasters, high interest rates charged by local financial institutions, limitation of loans availability and lack of information. The interviewed households that engaged in diversified livelihood strategies gained relatively more remittances than those that rely on on-farm livelihood strategies alone due to their high social network with their relatives living in towns and cities. Some of the households that were able to diversify their livelihood strategies indicated that they also earn money from their sons and daughters working in other regions in the country (e.g. Addis Ababa, Bahirdar, Debre Markos) since they invested in educating them.

4.3. Econometric Result Analysis

This section presents the results of the logistic regression analysis (outlined in chapter 3) and discusses results of the significant variables determining the choice of rural households' to off-farm livelihood strategies in East Gojjam Zone. The logistic regression model was used for testing the socio-economic factors that influence rural households in selecting all their existing off-farm livelihood strategies where the choice of off-farm livelihood strategies were treated as the dependent variables while the independent variables included amongst others age, gender, land size owned and access to market centers (as highlighted in chapter 3). The results of the logistic analysis of the hypothesized independent variables which were expected to affect the choice of rural households' livelihood strategies are provided in Table 4.2 below.

Table 4.2: Logit Estimates of Off-Farm Income Diversification Decision

Dependent variable	Off-farm income diversification				
Independent variables	Coefficients	Std. error	z-value	Marginal Effects	p>z
HHs' Characteristics					
Sex	0.1018	0.0411	2.48	0.0229***	0.009
Age	0.2372	0.1121	2.12	0.0413**	0.034
Age Square	-0.3415	0.1274	-2.68	-0.1299***	0.007
Health	-0.0442	0.0099	-4.44	-0.0052***	0.000
Education	0.5001	0.2071	2.42	0.0784**	0.016
Education Square	-0.4287	0.1422	-3.01	-0.0968***	0.003
HHs' Endowments					
Family Size	1.0695	0.609	1.76	0.2593*	0.077
Farm Size	-0.7982	0.2745	-2.91	-0.0074***	0.004
Community level Characteristics					
Mobile phone	0.5369	0.3059	1.76	0.1237*	0.084
Electricity	0.2556	0.1013	2.52	0.0574**	0.011
Transportation	-0.7204	0.3348	-2.15	-0.1606**	0.029
Market	-0.9426	0.2874	-3.27	-0.2117***	0.001
Transport*Market	0.7813	0.2613	2.99	0.1755***	0.003
Entry Barriers					
Social Capital	1.0674	0.3306	3.23	0.2478***	0.001

<i>Formal Credit</i>	1.0875	0.3834	2.84	0.2218***	0.001
Location Factor					
<i>Dejen</i>	0.4833	0.2079	2.32	0.0694**	0.020
	Number of Observations		620		
	Wald Chi Square		269***		
	Pseudo R ²		0.69		

Note: ***, ** and * denotes statistical significance at 1%, 5% and 10% levels respectively. Source: Authors' computation using STATA 14.

4.3.1. Gender of the respondents

On gender perspective, male headed households are more likely to diversify into off-farm income diversification activity than their female counterparts (See table 4.2 above). This is contradicting with the findings of Ali and Peerlings (2012) in Ethiopia. Female headed households are less likely to participate in off-farm activities than the male headed counterparts, and the corresponding marginal effect indicates that male headed households are 2.29 percentage points more likely than female headed households to participate in off-farm self employment activities, holding other covariates at their mean. This might be because of female headed families invest much time in domestic roles such as childcare, cooking, washing cloth, gathering fire wood, fetching water with high participation in low economic value and time consuming agricultural activities like weeding and harvesting. This is consistent with De Brauw *et al.*, (2002) and Shi *et al.*, (2007) findings, there was a clear gender bias in participation into off-farm activities. Men are much more likely to engage in any occupation (local wage employment, local self-employment and migration) rather than in farm labor than are women.

4.3.2. Ages of the respondents

Age of household head has a significant influence on off-farm income diversification decision hence; households with younger heads are more likely to diversify into off-farm income diversification activities. The marginal effect for age implies that as age of the household head increases from its mean value 48 to 49 years, the chance of being involved in off-farm activities

will increase by 4.13 percentage points, while other variables are kept at their mean. On the contrary, households with ageing heads are less likely to diversify into off-farm income diversification activities due to productivity decline associated with old age. This can be seen in the above table as age square has a negative figure. The result is consistent with the findings of Abdullai and Crolerees (2001) in their study of households in Mali. Explicitly speaking, the probability of participation in off-farm income diversification significantly decreases with age of the household head at 1% significance level. The marginal effect for age square implies that as age of the household head increases from its mean value 48 to 49 years, the chance of being involved in off-farm activities will decrease by 12.99 percentage points, while other variables are kept at their mean. This is consistent with theory and intuition that as household heads get old they become experienced on farming and need to spend more time on their farm instead of looking for off-farm activities. Another reason is as household heads get old they may not fit for physically hard off-farm activities.

4.3.3. Education

The estimates on education show that the effects of education on off-farm income diversification decision are indeed non-linear. The effects are significantly positive up to a certain educational level and it becomes negative thereafter, as indicated by the square coefficient. The nonlinear effect of education on off-farm diversification decision is consistent with the finding of Loening et al. (2008) on off-farm income diversification in rural Ethiopia. The positive coefficient 0.0784 implies that holding all other factors constant, lack of education has a potential of influencing households to move from on-farm livelihood strategy to off-farm livelihood strategy. A 1 level drop in the level of education attained by a household head from the highest expected level of education (tertiary level) will result in a 7.84% increase in the chance to shift from on-farm livelihood strategy to off-farm livelihood strategy. The results indicate that uneducated household heads have a positive probability of shifting from on-farm to off-farm livelihood strategy although De Brauw *et al.*, (2002) highlighted that households' knowledge, skill and attitude are shaped through education on how to diversify livelihood strategies. Where agriculture is poor; uneducated household heads resort to off-farm enterprises in nearby towns, brewing and selling home-made beer (*Tella, Teje, Areki*), remittances, borrowing, transfers and social grants as well as

doing piece jobs in neighboring villages. Research results in Table 4.2 indicate that uneducated households have a positive probability of engaging in off-farm livelihood strategy.

4.3.4. Family size

In this study, the family size was another determinant that influenced rural households to diversify their livelihood income generation into off-farm livelihood strategies. There was a significantly positive relationship between household livelihood off-farm diversification strategies and the increase in family size as indicated by the positive coefficients of 0.2593. This indicates that family size has a potential of influencing households to shift from on-farm livelihood strategy and engage in off-farm livelihood strategies. Holding all other factors constant, an increase in the size of the household by one member will result in a 25.93% increase in chances/probability of a household to shift from on-farm livelihood strategy to off-farm livelihood strategy by a household. Greater family sizes in the study area have a positive probability of shifting from on-farm livelihood strategy and engage in off-farm livelihood strategies and this conforms to what Reardon (1997) discovered. Reardon (1997) discovered that a larger family size increases the ability of a household to supply labour to the farm and hence to off-farm livelihood strategy. These households would only resort to off-farm livelihood strategy as the second best livelihood strategy to on-farm livelihood strategy during dry season. Some family members in larger households were migrating to closer towns and cities for off-farm employment while members from small households were fully based in the rural areas of the study area taking care of livestock and crops during the rainy season.

4.3.5. Farm size

The amount of land a farmer owns can be associated with the amount of produce obtained in a season *ceteris paribus*. It should, however, be acknowledged that it is not always the case that the available land will be fully utilized for farming. Farm size does show a significant effect in off-farm income diversification decision at 10% significant level. If we choose 10% significant level it significantly decreases the probability of participation in off-farm self-employment. A unit reduction in the farm size what the households have, will increase the probability that the households participate in off-farm income diversification activities by 0.74%. This finding confirms that there exists significant variation in land holding among the sample households as land is

expressed in per capita terms. This conforms to what De Brauw *et al.*, (2002) concluded in their research in China. In support of this finding, Abdulai and Crolerees (2001), reveal that households' land size has the expected sign and statistically significant. This result is consistent with our expectation as we anticipated the coefficient to be negative and significant effect on off-farm income diversification activities. Thus, land ownership probably is the major constraints that restricted households from owning large animal. This may therefore push households to diversify their livelihood strategies off-farm activities.

4.3.6. Credit access

The statistically significant coefficients of 0.2218 in Table 4.2 above indicate a positive relationship between the increase in the number of the sources of credit and the probability of the households to diversify their livelihood strategies into off-farm activities. Credit access has a potential of influencing households in the study area to shift from on-farm livelihood strategy to off-farm livelihood strategies. As the chances to access credit and the number of credit sources increases, the probability of households to engage into these livelihood strategies increases. Holding all other factors constant, an increase in access to credit by 1 extra source will result in 22.18% increases in chances to shift from on-farm livelihood strategy to off-farm livelihood strategies respectively. Most households in the study areas have a poor resource base; therefore providing credit to these households will improve their livelihoods. Access to educational loans builds a strong education base which may in turn increase job opportunities i.e. off-farm livelihood strategy. This conforms to what De Brauw *et al.*, (2002) concluded in their research in China.

4.3.7. Village groups and Cooperative membership

The logistic regression results of the survey reflected that as expected, the relationship between off-farm livelihood diversification ability and membership to a cooperative society, village groups as well as training was found positive and statistically significant. The result of entry barriers shows that households having access to social capital are more likely to diversify into off-farm income diversification activities than those without access. This indicates the importance of membership of associations in overcoming the entry barriers associated with off-farm income diversification. Associations such as cooperatives provide loans, financial assistance and information to their

members, thereby encouraging households' participation in off-farm entrepreneurial activities. The coefficient 0.2478 indicates that cooperatives have a potential of influencing households to move from on-farm livelihood strategy to off-farm livelihood strategy. Holding all other factors constant, a 1 unit increase in the number of cooperatives per individual household will result in a 24.78% increase in the probability of a household to shift from on-farm livelihood strategy to off-farm livelihood strategy. In support of this finding, Abdullai and Crolerees (2001) also pointed out that households with member to any cooperatives are in a better position to overcome the barriers to entry and hence, promotes off-farm income diversification. For instance, during the dry season when some water sources for agricultural cooperatives are dry, members of the cooperatives resort to other income generating activities like piece jobs and selling building materials like pit-sand and bricks (off-farm livelihood strategy). The money obtained from the cooperatives may be used for other off-farm income generating activities in dry seasons. This off-farm diversification of activities is meant to reduce risks of crop failure in local agricultural cooperatives.

4.3.8. Households' health status

Predictably, the findings on health status of the households have shown that household heads having any form of health disability are less likely to be involved in off-farm income diversification activities. This implies the importance of health to off-farm income diversification activities. Accordingly, the result of logit model reveals that the probability of participation in off-farm income activities will increase by 0.52% when households' health status become more and more healthy. In support of this finding, Abdullai and Crolerees (2001) also pointed out that, households with good health conditions are in a better position to promote off-farm income diversification. Similar studies suggest that good health condition have significant positive impact on off-farm income diversification activities in developing countries (Reardon et al., 1992; Lanjouw, 2001; Escobal, 2001; Ali and Peerling 2012).

4.3.9. Households' Community level characteristics

One of the determinants of engagement by rural households into off-farm livelihood strategies was market accessibility. The probability of the respondents to shift from on-farm livelihood strategy and engage in off-farm livelihood strategies decreases as the distance from a specific household to

the market centre or town increases. This relationship is indicated by the coefficients -0.2117 in Table 4.2 above. Holding all other factors constant, a 1km increase in the distance from a given rural household to the closest market centre will result in a 21.17% decline in the probability by a household to shift from on-farm livelihood strategy to off-farm livelihood strategies. Generally, as the households get situated closer to the markets centers or towns, the probability to diversify their livelihood strategies is very high. Households near market centers get several key advantages such as access to different information and terms of exchange for assets. They also save a lot of time, incur much lower transport costs and have better access to more remunerative off-farm and off-farm activities (Gebru and Beyene, 2012).

In support of this finding, Abdullai and Crolerees (2001) also pointed out that households with access to market are in a better position to overcome market constraints and develop private market initiatives that promotes off-farm income diversification. Access to infrastructure also plays an important role in determining diversification decision. For instance, households with access to electricity and mobile phone services are more likely to diversify into off-farm income diversification activities than those without access to such facilities by 5.74% and 12.37%, respectively. However, transportation access only increases the likelihood of diversification for households living far from the market as indicated by the positive coefficient of the market and transport interaction variable (17.55%). Similar studies suggest that access to transportation and electricity have significant positive impact on off-farm income diversification activities in developing countries (Reardon et al., 1992; Lanjouw, 2001; Escobal, 2001; Ali and Peerling 2012).

4.3.10. Location

Location dummy has also included as explanatory variable to capture other factors that create differences in participation decision of households in the two sample sites. An individual in Dejen districts' has high probability of participation in off-farm activities over those who live in, Shebel Berenta districts'. The estimates for marginal effects shows that keeping all variables at their mean, individuals in Dejen districts' have 6.94 percentage points more chance of participation in off-farm income diversification activities than its counterpart, Shebel Berenta districts'. This is reasonable as Dejen districts' is along the main road from Addiss Ababa to Bahirdar town which have relatively wider market than Shebel Berenta districts'. Another reason is that in Dejen district

there are a lot of factories that uses more of its domestic resources hence; there existed a forward and backward linkage in consumption and production activities, because of this large numbers of individuals got a permanent and temporary employment. But for Shebel Berenta districts' the nearby market is yeduha town, which has relatively smaller market for off-farm employment opportunities and till now there is no factories that has been established in the town even if the district is rich in natural resources. Therefore, the result confirms the differences in socio-economic characteristics and resource endowment of the two districts in the zones.

4.4. Constraints to off-farm income livelihood diversification in study areas.

Diversification of livelihood strategies is important for the rural households in the developing countries particularly in rural households. Rural households in the study areas are facing some problems to successful off-farm livelihood diversification. Identification of constraints for a particular agro-ecological region is crucial for future policy formulation as Gebru and Beyene (2012) suggests. Some of the challenges that include the socio-economic, technological, and institutional and policy challenges to rural livelihood diversification in the study areas are outlined in table 4.3 below. Some of the major challenges that were identified by the rural households in the study areas include: poor household asset base, poor rural infrastructure, lack of access to credit facilities, lack of awareness, shortage of training facilities, fear of taking risk, and lack of opportunities in off-farm sector.

Lack of capital: This is one of the major challenges to rural household off-farm livelihood diversification in these study areas. Chances to take up self-employment activities will be reduced by lack of access to capital in rural households. Ownership of assets which include bicycles ploughs and carts may enhance rural household diversification of livelihood strategies in rural households. A household that possesses a sewing machine may diversify livelihood strategies by venturing into fashion businesses. Possession of animals like donkeys, horses, cattle (for draught power) and carts may as well encourage individual rural households to take part in off-farm livelihood activities like transportation of goods for

money. Some of the rural households in the study area lack assets useful for self-employment and this act also as another obstacle to livelihood diversification.

Table 4.3: Rank of some major constraints to livelihood diversification in the study areas.

<i>List of possible Constraints</i>	<i>% Score</i>	<i>Rank/ Order</i>	<i>Most Affected Individuals in the study areas</i>
<i>Poor Asset Base/Capital</i>	95.6	1	<i>Small enterprises</i>
<i>Lack of Access to Credit</i>	83.5	2	<i>Non-agricultural labourers</i>
<i>Fear of Taking Risk</i>	76.3	3	<i>Petty business, casual labourers</i>
<i>Poor Infrastructure</i>	64.9	4	<i>Petty business, casual labourers</i>
<i>Lack of Awareness to Training</i>	51.7	5	<i>Small businesses, casual labourers</i>
<i>Lack of Opportunity</i>	48.2	6	<i>Small businesses, casual labourers</i>
<i>Unfavorable Climate Conditions</i>	42.0	7	<i>Agricultural cooperative members</i>

Source: survey results (2019)

Lack of access to credit facilities: Limited or lack of access to credit facilities is one of the major limiting factors to livelihood diversification in the study areas. In the absence of credit support from the institutional agencies, the resource poor households are not able to start their own off-farm business or enterprises (Geberu and Beyene, 2012). Credit facilities are important for livelihood diversification in poor rural households. Lack of access to credit facilities in rural households reduces the chances of participating in various off-farm income generating activities hence limited household livelihood diversification strategies. Households that fail to acquire loans from financial institutions due to lack of collateral are forced to engage themselves in less remunerative off-farm work and wage work. Individual money lenders charge very high interests on these rural households in the study area and this limits the participation to off-farm income diversification in rural areas in the study areas. Entrepreneurial skills acquired from government training in the rural households become less effective due to lack of access to credit by rural households in the study area.

Fear of taking risk: Lack of household assets in those households that were engaged in off-farm and on-farm livelihood strategies resulted in the lowering of the risk-bearing ability of these

rural households in this study area. Fear of taking risks in agriculture can as well reduce the chances of off-farm livelihood diversification in rural households in the study areas.

Poor infrastructure: Infrastructure plays an influential role in the development of rural livelihoods (Gebru and Beyene, 2012). Gebru and Beyene (2012) went on to indicate that improved communications help easy access to market which is important for both buying and selling of goods and services and for getting off-farm jobs. Good road network, effective telecommunications, electricity and clean water availability enhance economic development in the rural areas. Specifically this study area is one of the industrially backward rural areas of East Gojjam Zone due to poor infrastructure. Infrastructural bottlenecks also hamper industrial development in the study area. This can as well reduce the chances for rural household livelihood diversification in the study areas. Some of the villages are situated far away from the major tarred roads. Some rural households indicated that they have to travel a distance of about 6-14 km to reach the main road to access public transport. Towns cannot therefore be accessed easily by some of the rural households in remote areas of Shebel Berenta and Dejen districts'. This poses a serious obstacle to improvement in these rural households' off-farm livelihood strategies.

Lack of awareness and training: Lack of awareness and training in rural households reduce the chances of livelihood diversification in the study area. Not all rural households in the study area are aware of the schemes provided by the government for the development of the rural sector. Some of the rural households in the study area cannot even access the training programs offered by the government in the rural areas due to illiteracy and poor infrastructure. Some rural households lack information regarding modern income-generating activities due to limited information dissemination mechanisms from the government. Though technical subjects are now being offered in some schools in the zone, rural households still lack training in modern activities like dyeing and printing, welding, carpentry and bricklaying.

Lack of opportunities: Job opportunities for off-farm livelihood strategies, in some households, are very low. These opportunities may include access to accommodation in neighboring towns, access to government development programs and access to resources like clean water and

land. Lack of opportunities in some of the rural households in the study area reduces the chances of off-farm livelihood diversification in these households in the study areas.

Climate: The climate of rural areas in this study has generally unfavorable. Extreme temperatures, erratic rainfall, and water scarcity prevent some of the rural households to move from one place to another in search of a livelihood. Poor climatic conditions therefore reduce the chances of off-farm livelihood diversification in rural households in the study areas.

4.5. Effects of off-farm participation on households economic wellbeing in the study areas

To evaluate the effects of the off-farm participation on household economic wellbeing, the conditional expected both households' consumption expenditure and food shortage status by the off-farm participant households $E(y1|I = 1)$ is compared to what they would have enjoyed if they did not participate in off-farm activities $E(y0|I = 1)$. The difference in households' consumption expenditure and food shortage status conditional on off-farm participation is computed following equation (11) in chapter three and reported in Table 4.4 (a) and (b) below. It is also possible to compute the counterfactual hypothetical effects for the nonparticipants. However, due to the absence of a selection effect for the nonparticipants, that is, the nonparticipants are not different from random farmers; the counterfactual hypothetical effects are not taken into account.

The conditional expected households' consumption expenditure by the off-farm participant households $E(y1|I = 1)$ is approximately 16,245.64 ETH birr, while the conditional expected households' consumption expenditure that the same participant households would have enjoyed if they did not participate in off-farm work $E(y0|I = 1)$ is approximately 15,273.59 ETH birr. Therefore, when participating in off-farm activities, on average, rural farm households can make consumption expenditure gains of approximately 972.05 ETH birr per household member (See table 4.4 (a) below). This result reveals that participation in off-farm activities can allow rural farm households to increase their consumption expenditure. This finding is consistent with the widely held view in the literature that income from off-farm activities plays a vital role to smoothen household consumption expenditure.

Similarly, the endogenous switching model result shows that diversified households are more food secured than undiversified households. This implies that the increased household income from off-farm income diversification assist in significant reduction in food shortage experienced by the diversified households (See table 4.4 (b) below). Because off-farm employment generates supplementary household incomes, it can provide participants with additional capital for investments in agricultural technology, which is a productivity-enhancing factor. In addition to income generation, the farm households' engagement in off-farm employment can reduce the possibility of disguised unemployment as a result of excessive labor force on the farm, improving farm productivity and, thus, increasing the farm's output level. This finding is consistent with the widely held view in the literature that income from off-farm activities plays a vital role in improving food security status.

Table 4.4 (a). Effects Of Off-farm Participation On Household Consumption Expenditure

	Obs.	Mean	SD
$E(y_1 I=1)$	360	16,245.64	2402.45
$E(y_0 I=1)$	260	15,273.59	1569.31
ATT		972.05***	

Source: STATA outputs (2019)

Table 4.4 (b). Effects Of Off-farm Participation On Household Consumption Expenditure

	Obs.	Mean	SD
$E(y_1 I=1)$	360	0.49	0.50
$E(y_0 I=1)$	260	0.24	0.44
ATT		0.26***	

Source: STATA outputs (2019)

CHAPTER FIVE

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Introduction

This chapter draws conclusions from the above findings. The conclusions relate to the research sub-problems stated by proving answers of the research questions asked at the beginning of the study. Areas for further studies are also outlined in the study.

5.2. Conclusions

This study uses a cross sectional survey data of rural households from East Gojjam Zone to examine the determinants of off-farm income diversification among the farm households and its effects on their economic wellbeing. In their day to day economic living, rural farm households in East Gojjam Zone particularly in Shebel Berenta and Dejen districts rely on on-farm, off-farm, off-farm and/or their combinations as their livelihood strategies. Most households in the study area relied solely on off/off-farm livelihood strategy while only a few of rural households relied solely on agriculture as the main livelihood strategy. In the study areas, most young age households are engaged in more income diversification strategies and have densities of networks to build relations in and outside agriculture.

Given that resources are available, households in East Gojjam Zone are willing and able to diversify their livelihood strategies in to off-farm income generating activities. Hence, to estimate the determinants of off-farm income diversification decision, we have used/employed a logistic regression analysis. Accordingly, the logit model result in this study shows that off-farm income diversification decision is determined by household head characteristics, household endowments, community level characteristics and entry barriers. Explicitly speaking; among all the variables, the ones that significantly determine participation are, location, basic education attainment, cooperative membership, road network, health status, number of farm land owned, and mobile phone possession. These variables are found to have significant impact on diversification decision i.e. a positive change in these variables will increases the chances of diversifying the livelihood strategies in rural households in the study areas.

More pronouncedly, family size as one of the endowments of rural household has a significant positive impact on decision to participate in off-farm activities. Similarly, infrastructure at the community level, have an important influence on households' diversification decision. The results also indicate that households residing closer to local markets are more likely to diversify into off-farm activities than their counterparts in remote areas. In addition, in these study areas rural farm households having access to social and financial capital have managed to overcome the barriers associated with entry into off-farm activities. This is an interesting finding which has not been given much attention in previous studies and portrays the importance of social networking and loans in promoting off-farm activities in rural areas of East Gojjam Zone.

Moreover, in this study we have employed an endogenous switching model to examine the impacts of off-farm income on rural farm households' economic wellbeing by using total annual consumption expenditure and food shortage status of the households as indicators of economic wellbeing. The result shows that off-farm income diversification has a positive and significant impact on both the total annual consumption expenditure and food availability in the rural farm households'. This finding is consistent with the widely held view in the literature that income from off-farm activities plays a vital role to smoothen household consumption and in improving food security status.

In a nutshell, off-farm livelihood strategies were indicated by most of the respondents as best livelihood strategies to cope with different socio-economic household challenges and to improve their livelihoods in this poor rural area. These livelihood strategies provided a constant and continuous flow of income into rural households in the study area. On the other hand, off-farm livelihood strategies increased the level of rural household earnings and therefore, lead to a growth in earnings and consumption of most of the households in the study area. The livelihood assets discussed in this research study that include the role of human capital, financial capital, social capital and institutional supports are very important building block livelihood assets that can help marginalized rural households to diversify their livelihood income into off-farm activities in this study area. The rural households that had access to education, financial capital, or markets were wealthier than their counterparts. Access to remunerative opportunities varies across the poor households with youths, women, less and un-educated as well as other households lacking social ties in the community.

5.3. Recommendations

The findings of the study imply that any projects undertaken by the government and NGOs in aiming at sustainable improvement of poor rural households' livelihood in East Gojjam Zone should give attention to the following issues:

- ✓ Off-farm work plays very important role on the livelihood of the poorest of poor, because it is very important source of income for them next to crop income. Thus, respective bodies should work more on enhancing the livelihood of this segment of rural households by introducing interventions that support the development of off-farm sector and hence, poor households can participate and benefit directly from the sector.
- ✓ Diversification of off-farm livelihood strategy needs to be strengthened in rural farm households in the study areas. One way to strengthening the diversification of off-farm income activities to through education, training and awareness; therefore, rural farm households in East Gojjam Zone should acquire formal and informal education, vocational training and awareness on how they can venture into, run businesses and engage on better income generating livelihood activities to cope with economic constraints in the area,
- ✓ While this paper is not advocating for off-farm income activities as a substitute to farming, off-farm work could be a reliable complement to farming activities. Policy should therefore focus on making off-farm work opportunities available to rural households and help them overcome entry barriers. Such measures may include increasing the access of rural households to physical, financial, social and human capital. Physical capital measures such as good roads, dependable electricity supply and general infrastructural development will help to reduce production and transportation costs. Improving access to education in rural communities would also enhance off-farm employment opportunities, particularly, off-farm wage employment.
- ✓ The study shows that membership of a village group and rural cooperatives have a positive association with off-farm work participation in the study areas. Thus, promotion of the formation and participation in village groups and associations (i.e. cooperatives, women associations, business associations, and farmer-based organizations), will go a long way in enhancing off-farm employment opportunities for rural farm households in the study areas.

Therefore, these types of associations should be encouraged among the rural farm households.

- ✓ Even though they have more probability to participate in off-farm income generating activities, female headed households earn lower than their counterparts from these activities. This is because most of them are involved in low return small scale traditional off-farm activities like: weaving, spinning, pottery and preparing local drinks like ‘Tella’ and ‘Tegi’, selling tea or coffee and shop keeping. Thus, they should be provide with skill enhancing training in order to improve the quality of commodities they provide and get attractive return from these activities. And they should also be provide with low interest rate credit which can help them to enlarge the scale of their enterprises, hence could reduce costs related with those activities and make them profitable.
- ✓ Proximity to towns (i.e. the district towns) contributed to the engagement of rural farm household in off-farm livelihood diversification which would suggest the need to expanding emerging towns in different districts of the zone.
- ✓ Finally, older household heads are less likely to participate in off-farm activities than its young counterparts even earn less in case they participate. Thus, the governmental and non governmental agencies should find sustainable aid to those old ages because they cannot supplement their agriculture with other sources.

5.4. Areas of future studies

Although we find that off-farm income diversification has positive effects on consumption expenditure and food security status of rural farm households in the study areas, we cannot conclude whether it is the poor or the non-poor that benefits from off-farm livelihood strategies in rural economy. Thus, further research is still needed to fill this gap. Moreover, rural households engaged in similar household livelihood strategies differ in terms of levels of wealth. Hence, the causes of and wealth value margins need to be assessed both at household levels and at community levels. Therefore, further research is still needed to fill this gap. Finally, in this investigation we didn’t examine the impact of the heterogeneity in terms of the economic activities to spell out the effect of off-farm income diversification on the economic wellbeing of rural households’ in the study areas. Therefore, further research is still needed to fill this gap.

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